

A COMPREHENSIVE FRAMEWORK FOR JOB DESCRIPTION MANAGEMENT:
INTEGRATION OF WORKDAY, BOX, AND GREENHOUSE FOR ENHANCED
COMPLIANCE AND EFFICIENCY

Shweta Pandey
shweta1780@gmail.com

Sumit Pandey
sumpandey@gmail.com

Abstract

Job descriptions are crucial to the recruitment process, impacting employers, employees, and recruiters alike. Having a well-written, clear, and concise job description is essential, but as an organization grows and the number of templates increases, managing them becomes challenging. Streamlining the job description management and approval process is vital to simplify hiring and avoid complications. This article delves into organization membership security groups, business process workflows, and document management to establish a system for tracking job description management and approval. Additionally, it discusses specific tools and customizable solutions offered by Workday, Box, and Greenhouse to facilitate this process.

Keywords: Workday, Box, Greenhouse, Job Description, organization membership security groups, Business Process, Job Description Management.

I. INTRODUCTION

Job description management is a vital practice for organizations to streamline the recruitment process and manage expectations for specific positions [2]. Job descriptions include components like company and department overviews, employment type and benefits, and contact information [1,2,13]. They also play a critical role in complying with federal and state employment regulations [4,5].

Given that these descriptions contain crucial information shared with external candidates, it is essential to have a robust system for creating, updating, and approving job description documents [1,2,3,5]. This involves designated teams such as Human Resources, Communications, and Compliance. As a company grows, managing job descriptions becomes challenging due to their existence in isolated states – within departments, on shared drives, or with specific individuals [2]. This lack of governance leads to inefficiencies, complexities, and inconsistencies, potentially resulting in costly hiring mistakes [2].

It is very common for companies today to have separate Human Capital Management (HCM) and Recruiting systems [12], creating a need for seamless integration between them. To address the issues of job description management and approval, these processes should be integrated with HCM and Recruiting systems. Generic components such as company and department

overviews, employment type and benefits, and federal and state employment regulations [1,2,13] should be automated to ensure accuracy and compliance, preventing hiring managers or recruiters from making inadvertent errors.

II. PROBLEM STATEMENT

Effective job descriptions offer numerous benefits [1], including improved recruitment, transparency, legal compliance, communication, conflict resolution, and strategic planning [4]. While having well-crafted job descriptions is crucial, it is equally important to establish a streamlined approval process [2,3]. Regardless of who drafts the job description, the company should designate a person or team responsible for its approval [3,5]. This team must ensure that the job description is complete, accurate, free of legal issues, and maintains uniformity in look, tone, and feel [2,5]. Although job description management [2] software(s) are available, it often cannot seamlessly integrate with HCM and Recruiting systems and may incur additional costs. Thus, organizations need an integrated solution for job description document management and approval within their HCM systems, also ensuring the audit trail remains within the HCM framework.

Specific sections of job descriptions, such as those related to company and department information or federal and state regulations [2,13], should be maintained by designated teams like Human Resources (HR), Communications or Compliance. These sections should not be editable by hiring managers or recruiters. Instead, hiring managers or recruiters should add position-specific details, while pre-defined sections are automatically appended through the business process workflow of job description management and approval.

III. SOLUTION

3.1 Workday Tools & Technology

3.1.1 Security groups

Workday offers organization membership security groups [6] to set security permissions for employees in specified organizations, which can include types such as Company, Cost Center, or Department. These security groups can be created for different teams - Human Resources, Communication, and Compliance that participate in the approval workflow process of job descriptions.

3.1.2 Business Process

Workday provides two customizable business process definitions to accommodate approval steps from HR, Communication, or Compliance teams. The 'Create Position' [7] process tracks the flow when a new position is created, and its job description defined. The 'Edit Position Restrictions' [8] process is used to modify hiring restrictions, including the job description of an existing position. Workday's rich text formatting feature for job description fields [7] can be utilized in these processes, which can be customized to include approval steps for reviewing and approving job descriptions.

3.1.3 Workday Studio

Workday Studio is an integration option that allows organizations to build, own, and support sophisticated integrations hosted and run by Workday [9]. These integrations can be launched in various scenarios, including automatically as part of a business process [9]. Custom integrations can connect to document management tools where job description templates are maintained, appending generic sections to the job description in Workday.

Fig 1: Organization membership security group for Compliance team

Business Process Steps		Notifications	Allowed Actions by Role	Allowed Services	Allowed Subprocess For	Related Links	Available Rules & Fields		
Business Process Steps 8 items									
Step	Order	If	Type	Specify	Step Label Override	Supporting Information	Optional	Group	
Q	a		Initiation				No		
Q	a1	Parent process is pending or has completed but does not have a Change Organization task already started.? (Workday Owned)	Action	Change Organization Assignments			No	Initiator	
Q									
Q	c1		Action	Review Position Request		Yes	No	Communications Reviewer	
Q	c2		Action	Review Position Request		Yes	No	Compliance Reviewer	

Fig 2: 'Create Position' business process definition including approval step for Communication and Compliance team

Job Posting Title *
Number of Positions *
Hiring Restrictions
Qualifications
Availability Date *
Earliest Hire Date *
No Job Restrictions
Job Family
Job Profiles for Job Family (empty)
Job Profile
Job Description Summary
Job Description

Fig 3: Create Position task page highlighting the rich text formatted Job Description field

Business Process Steps Notifications Allowed Actions by Role Allowed Services Allowed Subprocess For Related Links

Business Process Steps 25 items

Step	Order	If	Delay	Type	Specify	Step Label Override	Optional	Group
Q	a			Initiation			No	
Q	a1							
Q	a1							
Q	Configure INT...	b1		Integration			No	

Fig 4: Business Process definition highlighting step to invoke an Integration

3.2 Box

Document Management for Job Descriptions - Box allows companies to create and share content seamlessly and securely. It can be used to organize, edit, share, store, and classify content within a secure document management system [10]. Communication and Compliance teams can be responsible for creating and maintaining job description templates in Box. Templates can include generic sections for company-specific information based on parameters like department, sub-department, country, and state. Documents can be organized using

custom metadata and tags, which the Workday Studio Integration can use to append generic sections to job descriptions in Workday.

3.3 Greenhouse Recruiting

Greenhouse provides HRIS link integration with Workday to import positions [11]. This integration ensures that every new position in Workday syncs to Greenhouse Recruiting as a new job with a single opening [11]. Field mapping can sync the job description field from Workday to Greenhouse, where it can be posted on the company's career portal. Security permissions can be set in Greenhouse to prevent recruiters from editing job descriptions already approved by designated teams in Workday.

3.4 Process Flow

The process begins in the HCM system, Workday, where positions are created and managed. Hiring managers or recruiters populate position details like department, sub-department, location, and job description when creating or editing positions. This triggers approval steps for teams such as Communication or Compliance to review the roles and responsibilities specific to the position. Once all approvals are completed, the business process event is marked as complete. The final step in the Business Process involves calling a custom Workday Studio Integration, which extracts the job description template from Box using parameters like department, sub-department, and location. This integration updates the job description by appending generic texts (company and department overview, benefits, location-specific details, federal and state regulations) and marks the position as 'Ready' for sync to Greenhouse. The HRIS link integration then syncs the open position from Workday to Greenhouse, creating a Job Requisition with the approved job description for posting.

Fig 5: Process Flow

IV. LIMITATIONS AND FUTURE SCOPE

While this custom solution aims to automate the job description process involving Workday, Greenhouse, and Box, several areas remain unaddressed. The following points highlight key limitations of this custom solution:

- The primary objective of this solution is to automate the preparation of job descriptions for posting after obtaining all necessary approvals. Ideally, the approved job description should seamlessly flow from Workday, and recruiters with 'Job Admin' permission in Greenhouse should be restricted from updating it. However, since recruiters must also be able to create job posts and there is a common permission for creating and editing job posts [14], it is currently not possible to prevent recruiters from editing the already approved job descriptions directly on the job posts.
- In the proposed solution, once the communications team updates the job description templates in Box, these changes will only apply to newly created job posts. Existing posted jobs will not reflect these updates, leading to inconsistencies in the generic sections of the job descriptions. The only way to rectify this issue is through manual updates.

These limitations suggest directions for future research. Greenhouse's API library offers potential solutions for updating data programmatically. A deeper investigation into the 'Job Board API' and 'Harvest API' provided by Greenhouse [15] could reveal methods to enhance this solution and address these limitations. Additionally, implementing an event-based integration from Box to update already posted job descriptions would further extend the capabilities of the custom solution discussed in this article.

V. IMPACT

The custom solution leveraging organization membership security, Workday's business process framework, document management in Box with custom metadata and tags, and Greenhouse's HRIS link integration significantly enhances job description management within an organization. By recording all details and approvals within the HCM application, this solution improves transparency and accountability. Storing all job description templates in Box, maintained solely by the Communication and Compliance teams, and restricting recruiters and hiring managers to populate only the position-specific sections prevents legal and compliance issues. This setup grants the Communication and Compliance teams greater control over job descriptions posted on the company's career portal.

The configurable business process framework in Workday ensures compliance with organizational standards and policies. Integrating and automating processes from position creation to job posting for external candidates reduces manual steps and minimizes the risk of errors. This comprehensive solution streamlines the job description management and approval process, ensuring accuracy, compliance, and efficiency.

VI. CONCLUSION

Enhanced Governance and Compliance: The integrated solution ensures strict adherence to organizational standards and legal requirements, centralizing control with the Communication and Compliance teams to avoid legal and compliance issues.

Improved Efficiency and Accuracy: Automating the job description creation, updating, and approval processes significantly reduces manual intervention, minimizing errors and inconsistencies. This leads to more accurate and reliable job descriptions.

Seamless Integration: Seamless integration between Workday, Box, and Greenhouse ensures the job description management process is fully integrated within the HCM and Recruiting systems, enabling a smooth transition from job creation to job posting.

Enhanced Transparency and Accountability: Recording all details and approvals within the HCM application enhances transparency and accountability, ensuring every step of the job description process is tracked and documented.

Centralized and Controlled Document Management: Utilizing Box for document management provides a centralized repository of job description templates, maintained by the Communication and Compliance teams, and controlled access ensures that only designated personnel can modify specific sections, maintaining the integrity and consistency of job descriptions.

REFERENCES

1. CongressFoundation.org, "Developing job descriptions," Nov. 2012. [Online]. Available: https://www.congressfoundation.org/storage/documents/CMF_Pubs/cmf-developing-job-descriptions.pdf
2. JDXpert, "What is Job Description Management?," What is Job Description Management?, Aug. 27, 2021. <https://blog.jdexpert.com/what-is-job-description-management>
3. CHRS Recruiting Training Team, CHRS Recruiting Guide Series Position Descriptions. 2019. [Online]. Available: https://www.csustan.edu/sites/default/files/groups/Human%20Resources%2C%20Equal%20Opportunity%2C%20and%20Compliance/recruiting/rec_rg_09_position_descriptions.pdf
4. C. Ceplenski, "4 Benefits of effective job descriptions," HR Daily Advisor, Nov. 04, 2013. <https://hrdailyadvisor.blr.com/2013/11/05/4-benefits-of-effective-job-descriptions/>
5. "Who's approving your job descriptions? - HR Daily Advisor," HR Daily Advisor, May 18, 2015. <https://hrdailyadvisor.blr.com/2011/04/11/who-s-approving-your-job-descriptions/>
6. "Create Organization Membership Security Groups", June 18, 2021. <https://doc.workday.com/admin-guide/en-us/authentication-and-security/configurable-security/security-groups/membership-security-groups/lqv1575506220519.html?toc=2.2.6.1>
7. "Create Positions", June 18, 2021. <https://doc.workday.com/admin-guide/en->

- us/human-capital-management/staffing/maintain-positions/vqu1652492621549.html?toc=4.8.0
8. "Change Position Restrictions", June 18, 2021. <https://doc.workday.com/admin-guide/en-us/human-capital-management/staffing/maintain-positions/pga1652743258564.html>
 9. "Concept: Workday Studio", June 18, 2021. <https://doc.workday.com/admin-guide/en-us/workday-studio/studio-fundamentals/ebp1499866049976.html>
 10. "Document Management System | One Secure Platform | Box," Box, Mar. 21, 2016. <https://www.box.com/collaboration/document-management>
 11. "Greenhouse Recruiting with Workday® position management," Greenhouse Support, Nov. 2021. <https://support.greenhouse.io/hc/en-us/articles/360029579691-Greenhouse-Recruiting-with-Workday-position-management>
 12. E. McMichael, "The ATS recruiting smackdown: How your HCM stacks up to an all-in-one talent platform," iCIMS | the Leading Cloud Recruiting Software, Oct. 27, 2021. <https://www.icims.com/blog/the-ats-recruiting-smackdown-how-your-hcm-stacks-up-to-an-all-in-one-talent-platform/>
 13. K. Miller, "The 5 basic parts of a lucrative job posting," Apr. 03, 2020. <https://www.linkedin.com/pulse/5-basic-parts-lucrative-job-posting-kaitlin-cuvala/>
 14. "Edit external job post," Greenhouse Support, Nov. 12, 2021. <https://support.greenhouse.io/hc/en-us/articles/115002791566-Edit-external-job-post>
 15. "Greenhouse API overview," Greenhouse Support, Nov. 29, 2021. <https://support.greenhouse.io/hc/en-us/articles/10568627186203-Greenhouse-API-overview>